

PROMOTION OF NAGPUR CITY AS CONVENTION AND EXHIBITION CENTRE FOR MICE TOURISM

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Abstract:

Travel and tourism today is considered to be the world's largest industry. It has become a larger giant in terms of employment, investments, output and value. Convention tourism- a new type of tourism- is one form of tourism which is gaining popularity in the national and international business of the world. Convention is meeting of delegates or representative's conventions are planned and co-ordinate by professional meetings and convention planners. Most large cities have convention center dedicated to hosting such events. The term MICE- meeting, incentive, conventions / conferences and exhibition- is widely used in Asian Industries. Nagpur city also can be developed by convention market from Tourism & Hospitality point of view.

Keywords: *Promotion of tourism, MICE*

Introduction

India has been a buzz word in the economic crisis since over a score the world started coming to India post 1991. Business across sectors started gaining ground and complementing this growth, a parallel industry started emerging that titled towards knowledge enhancement, education, discussions, forums, symposium etc. leading to more conventions, conferences & seminars wherein the renowned speakers from all over the countries & professionals started making entry into the country analyzing & deliberating on what the future hold especially in developing regions. India soon started playing host to International & national conferences, seminars, symposiums, forums that demanded quality

infrastructure. One & only one PRAGATI Maidan in New Delhi seemed to be a too mediocre in comparison to the existing demands so a number of states of the art convention centers were being constructed such as Hyderabad International Convention centre(HICC) in India which proved to be very vital for this sector of tourism.

Apart from HICC few hospitality brands built hotels keeping in mind the swelling demand for quality MICE infrastructure & incorporated large conventions facilities in their plans. Mumbai the commercial capital of India has been debating for years to set up a state of the art convention facility but nothing major has moved yet from the discussion stage.

However from what we were to what we are & what we will be seems to reflect a rather positive picture. MICE in India are growing like anything & large conferences, conventions have gone beyond to grade A&B cities. The incentive market has shown an inclination towards the unconventional, the more exotic a place for mixing business with pleasure, the better. The fact however cannot be denied that for a country whose outbound MICE sector is being wooed by countries across the world, India as a MICE destination is still undersold for which an aggressive marketing in International level is the need of the hour for India to find an important place on the global MICE map.

Need for Infrastructure

The road connectivity between Nagpur & nearby tourist destinations which have not been yet explored or brought into limelight by the government needs to be improved in order to attract the MICE tourists into the city. Smaller destinations like Chikhaldara & others have immense opportunities but lack proper infrastructure, awareness & communication. Nagpur airport also lacks the capacity to handle large passenger traffic. However if the state government understands the importance of setting up a dedicated convention centre which is just on the talks & pursues it, the investigators sincerely felt that the tourist attraction hospitality. Strong cultural background, Safety & security would emerge Nagpur as an ideal MICE destination which has immense potential as far as a MICE destination is concerned.

With the launch of New properties such as Radisson coming up in Nagpur this will cater to the conferencing & banqueting needs of the sector. But to make it large the Maharashtra government should explore the possibility of opening up a large convention facility through active participation which can accommodate more delegates. It can also sell its tourism potential & strengths to lure business houses to host their conventions in the city.

MICE (i.e. Meeting, Incentive, Conference and Exhibition) is an acronym which is inconsistently applies with 'E' sometimes referring to events and the 'C' sometimes referring to conventions. MICE is used to refer to a tourism of a particular type in which a preplanned large group for a particular purpose. MICE tourism is a very well planned agenda that center around a particular theme such as hobby, profession or an educational topic. The MICE events are normally planned by the convention bureaus or convention centers located in various cities. The entire process of marketing and planning is conducted well before the actual event sometimes before several years. MICE tourism is known for its flawless planning and demanding clientele.

These are the definitions as put out by IAPCO (the International Association of Professional Congress Organizers):

Meeting- General term indicating the coming together of a number of people in one place, to confer or carry out a particular activity. Frequency: can be on an ad hoc basis or according to a set pattern, as for instance annual general meetings, committee meetings, etc.
Incentive- Meeting event as part of a program which is offered to its participants to reward a previous performance.

Conference Participatory meeting designed for discussion, fact-finding, problem solving and consultation. As compared with a congress, a conference is normally smaller in scale and more select in character - features which tend to facilitate the exchange of information. The term "conference" carries no special connotation as to frequency. Though not inherently limited in time, conferences are usually of limited duration with specific objectives.

Exhibition- Events at which products and services are displayed.

The "E" sometimes referring to Events and the "C" sometimes referring to Conventions.

MICE tourism is a growing sector and is becoming the latest trend in the India's tourism industry. Every year, between September and February, good number of foreign tourists visits India to attend various exhibitions, conferences or seminars. India Convention Promotion Bureau (ICPB) is a specialized agency of the Govt. of India, Ministry of Tourism.

Recently in India, many international conferences were organized by many companies to attract thousands of delegates. All these events placed India at a strong footing in conference segment. For MICE sector, India has unique advantage because it can offer exciting pre and post-convention tours.

Aim: To promote Nagpur city as Convention & Exhibition Centre for MICE Tourism.

Objectives:

- To study world convention market from tourism and hospitality point of view.
- To study Indian convention industry from tourism & hospitality point of view.
- To study market potentiality & other Indian cities to increase convention business.
- To study convention facilities in hotels of Nagpur.
- To study the role convention business in the development of tourism & hospitality industry of Nagpur.

Research methodology:

A method is more than an interrelation of techniques or a technique general enough to be used in several disciplines. On the other hand a methodology is the analytical study of methods. Specific studies are herein examined as to the techniques adopted, the manner in which they are applied the assumption made and the result obtained.

The survey on study of “Promotion of Nagpur city as convention and exhibition Centre for MICE Tourism” is taken from literature, internet and through the questionnaires. Sample was selected from the tourist visiting conventions and exhibition related to Tourism and Hospitality held at Kasturchand Park and Hotel Centre Point.

A general survey was conducted to get information of current situations of inbound convention and exhibition tourism in India. The area for the research was limited to the Kasturchand Park and Hotel Centre Point of Nagpur city. On the basis of pilot study on convention and exhibition business in Nagpur city to carry out the study on “Promotion of Nagpur city as convention and exhibition centre for MICE tourism” the sample was collected from the exhibitions and conventions held in Kasturchand Park and Hotel Centre Point in Nagpur city. Sample size of 100 samples was selected for conducting the research (50 stall exhibitors and organizers & 50 visitors).

Primary data was collected from the questionnaire and personal interaction with event organizers & exhibition & sample collection from other general events held in Nagpur city. Secondary data was collected from the sources such as Statistical bulletins, Magazines about Travel and trade Expo in India and Nagpur, material provided by the leading travel agencies in Nagpur city and web pages from the internet. The data collected was analyzed and interpreted with the help of statistical tabulation method & by percentage method and presented through graphs & pie charts.

Result and Discussion:

The analysis show that there is tremendous potentiality of convention business in Nagpur city as it is centrally located in India. From the research it is clear that the government and non-government agencies in Nagpur have started working for making the Nagpur city as conventional and exhibition destination for mice tourism. Following are the result and discussion carried out front ha data collected:

As shown in the figure it is seen that 42% of visitors of exhibition & organization said that role of ministry should take initiative steps for the development of convention increase in infrastructure 30% of site & rest 20% & 8% for professional development and other resources respectively.

Frequency of attending conferences & meetings

As shown in the figure, the investigator found that 50% respondents, exhibitors/organizers / visitors would travel to Nagpur once a year for attending meeting and conferences, 30% visitors said that they travelled for event in Nagpur for the first time and 20% visitors said that they travel for attending events twice a year.

Further research shows that 50% of the exhibition organizers requires convention hall to organize any conference & meeting and 30% said that they require food court and rest 10% said other tourism recreation facilities are required.

When questioned about the impact of holding convention & exhibition in Nagpur, the investigator found that about 50% respondents said that impact of holding convention & exhibition in Nagpur will boost business opportunities, 25% of the guests said the flow of tourist arrival will increase & rest 25% said that it will increase the networking technology.

Summary and Conclusion:

The project undertaken was “Promotion Nagpur city as Convention & Exhibition Centre for MICE Tourism”. The survey was conducted in the city Nagpur to know the potentiality of convention tourism at Nagpur city. The survey was held among the local

tourists and tour operators. The questionnaire was circulated among the officials/ organizers of specific event convention & exhibition which were held in the city from 2007-2011.

The survey gave results describing where Nagpur tourism is developed and where it needs to be popularized and maintained.

The researcher, from this research found that the Nagpur city has tremendous potential convention business due to entrance of ministry affairs in winter time as all the ministry people visits Nagpur city at the time of the 'Winter Session' of the Maharashtra.

The project successfully studied the tourist distinctions and highlighted the wildlife destination spots in and around Nagpur to provide the exhibitor and visitor of event held in Nagpur city and suggest the ways to and how to popularize the convention business in the Nagpur city.

Thus, it brings to the conclusion that survey has touched some important aspects for promoting convention and exhibition business in Nagpur city. The study revealed that Nagpur has lot of potentials in Nagpur for convention business to take off in the coming future and Nagpur can make a key as a National/ International convention destinations for MICE tourism.

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